

IRISCC

D6.8

Technical test procedure for approving integrated IRISCC digital services

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Abstract

Key words

Technical test procedure, VRE, CI/CD, D4Science, SonarQube

Task 6.4 focused on designing and implementing a test procedure for newly integrated and developed IRISCC Scientific and Knowledge Services. The procedure ensures technical interoperability, validates readiness for operational deployment, and supports inclusion in the IRISCC Catalogue of Services (Work Package, WP, 7). It is aligned with ENVRI-Hub NEXT project's best practices, including Continuous Integration/Continuous Delivery/Deployment (CI/CD) pipelines, SonarQube-based source code analysis, aims to enhance the FAIR compliance, and integration with WP9 and WP10 service provision workflows. The D4Science VRE (Virtual Research Environment) has been designated as the operational platform for IRISCC demonstrators, providing a collaborative and scalable infrastructure for service development, operational testing, and deployment.

Overall this deliverable D6.8 sets the ground preparing the IRISCC demonstrators to be integrated in the D4Science IRISCC VRE, IRISCC Catalogue of Services and the ENVRI HUB as partner for long-term sustainability. Thus, the new VRE will serve as a valuable platform for the IRISCC project demonstrations, facilitating research integration, collaboration, and open science practices.

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Main Author(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ulrich Bundke (FZJ) • Dick M.A. Schaap (MARIS) 		
Contributing Authors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tjerk Krijger (MARIS) • Contact person of IRISCC Demonstrators: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Valérie Thouret (CNRS, IAGOS) • Contact persons of D4Science Teams: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Massimiliano Assante (CNR-ISTI) ○ Leonardo Candela (CNR-ISTI) ○ Pasquale Pagano (CNR-ISTI) 		
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Key Terminology / Acronyms

Term/Acronym	Definition
ACTRIS	Aerosol, Clouds, and Trace gases Research infrastructure: A research infrastructure that focuses on the observation of aerosols, clouds, and trace gases.
API	Application Programming Interface
CCP	The Cloud Computing Platform is a sophisticated system of distributed components encompassing different technological and operational domains.
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Delivery/Deployment
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure: EGI is the federation of computing and storage resource providers united by a mission of delivering advanced computing and data analytics services for research and innovation.
EIRENE	European Infrastructure for Environmental Routine Observation Networks: A European infrastructure for routine environmental observations.
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud: An open science cloud that provides researchers in Europe with access to data, computing resources, and services.
EVERSE	European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable: A set of principles for research data management that ensure data is easily discoverable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.
FR	Functional Requirements
IAGOS	In-service Aircraft for Global Observing System: A global observing system that conducts measurements of trace gases and aerosols in the atmosphere.
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observing System: An integrated system for observing the carbon cycle.
ICT	Information and Communication Technology. Here e.g. the adoption of Microservice development resulted in substantial improvements of

	interoperability and composability of software components even when these components are distributed across a network.
IRISCC	Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change risks
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
NFR	Non-Functional Requirements
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OR	Organisational Requirements
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST	Representational State Transfer
RIs	European Research Infrastructures: Research infrastructures are facilities that are essential for conducting research.
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UI	User Interface
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time
VLAB	Virtual Laboratory
VRE	Virtual Research Environment: A virtual environment that provides researchers with tools and resources for collaboration and conducting research projects.
WCAG	Web W3C Content Accessibility Guidelines
WP	Project's Work Package

Table of Contents

Executive summary	6
1 Introduction.....	8
1.1 Objective of this report.....	8
2 Scope.....	9
3 Testing framework.....	10
3.1 Criteria/principles.....	10
3.1.1 Accessibility and internationalisation.....	10
3.1.2 Availability and Security.....	11
3.1.3 Code quality and Maintainability.....	12
3.1.4 Organisational requirements.....	12
3.1.5 Code quality standards.....	13
3.1.6 Documentation.....	13
3.2 Introduction to IRISCC D4Science VRE.....	14
3.3 Introduction to SonarQube for IRISCC Developers.....	15
4 Test categories & procedure	17
4.1 Test Procedure Design.....	17
4.2 Evaluation Criteria.....	18
4.3 Integration Workflow.....	18
4.4 Integration with D4Science Virtual Research Environment (VRE).....	19
4.5 Compliance Checklist for IRISCC Service Owners.....	19
4.5.1 Source Code Management.....	19
4.5.2 Code Quality and Testing.....	20
4.5.3 FAIR Compliance.....	20
4.5.4 Software Stack and Standards.....	20
4.5.6 Integration and Deployment.....	20
4.5.7 Documentation and Communication.....	21
4.6 Test process.....	21
5 Implementation	21
5.1 Catalogue of Services integration.....	21

5.2 Implementation plan.....	22
6 Conclusion	22
6.1 Outcomes	22
6.2 Lessons Learned and Recommendations	23
6.3 Next Steps.....	23
7 References.....	24

Executive summary

IRISCC is a Horizon Europe project that aims to provide **Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change risks**. Its goal is to foster cutting-edge research and evidence-based policymaking to improve Europe's resilience to climate change. The project focuses on developing **scientific and knowledge services** that leverage existing research infrastructures and data to address climate-related challenges. This includes areas such as extreme weather events, biodiversity loss, and food security. By combining data from various sources and providing advanced analytical tools, IRISCC aims to support climate change research and inform decision-making.

Work Package (WP) 6 of the IRISCC project aims to harmonise access procedures for research infrastructures and digital services and develop integrated services using the D4Science Virtual Research Environment (VRE).

Task 6.4 focused on designing and implementing a test procedure for newly integrated and developed IRISCC Scientific and Knowledge Services. The procedure ensures technical interoperability, validates readiness for operational deployment, and supports inclusion in the IRISCC Catalogue of Services (WP7). It is aligned with ENVRI-Hub NEXT project's best practices, including CI/CD (Continuous Integration / Continuous Delivery/Deployment) pipelines, SonarQube-based source code analysis, aims to enhance the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) compliance, and integration with WP9 and WP10 service provision workflows. The D4Science VRE has been designated as the operational platform for IRISCC demonstrators, providing a collaborative and scalable infrastructure for service development, operational testing, and deployment.

D4Science VRE is a cutting-edge VRE designed to facilitate collaborative scientific research. It provides a centralised platform where researchers from diverse disciplines can share data, resources, and computational tools. By leveraging advanced technologies, D4Science enables seamless integration and interoperability of heterogeneous data sources, fostering new insights and discoveries.

SonarQube is an open-source platform designed to continuously inspect and improve the quality of source code. It plays a critical role in modern software development by providing automated analysis of codebases, identifying bugs, security vulnerabilities, code smells,

and ensuring adherence to coding standards. For demonstrator service developers, SonarQube offers a robust mechanism to maintain high standards of code quality, reliability, and security throughout the development lifecycle. SonarQube was chosen by ENVRI-Hub NEXT as a testing tool ensuring high code quality and operational security. By adapting/aligning to the ENVRI HUB Next best practices the long-term sustainability and uptake of IRISCC services in the ENVRI HUB is enabled.

The IRISCC Project benefits from D4Science VRE by providing:

- **Centralised Platform:** Integrates various services and data for efficient research workflows.
- **Open Science Practices:** Promotes FAIR principles for data management and sharing.
- **Scalability and Flexibility:** Adapts to accommodate diverse research needs.
- **Enabling Collaboration and Knowledge Exchange:** Enables seamless collaboration among researchers.

Roadmap Development onboarding the IRISCC Demonstrators to the D4Science VRE:

- The deliverable D6.8 provides a brief description of the software tools of D4Science and SonarQube needed for a professional service deployment environment.
- It outlines a roadmap for integrating these demonstrators' data and services into CI/CD workflows needed for a potential ENVRI HUB uptake as long sustainability solution.
- The roadmap includes steps like initial meetings, workshops guiding technical discussions to ensure a smooth integration process.

Overall D6.8 sets the ground preparing the IRISCC demonstrators to be integrated in the D4Science IRISCC VRE, IRISCC Catalogue of Services and the ENVRI HUB as partner for long-term sustainability. Thus, the new VRE will serve as a valuable platform for the IRISCC project demonstrations, facilitating research integration, collaboration, and open science practices.

1 Introduction

1.1 Objective of this report

The primary objectives of Task 6.4 of IRISCC Work Package 6 (WP6) were to:

- Define and implement a test procedure that ensures the technical and operational quality of IRISCC services.
- Align service development and validation with ENVRI-Hub NEXT [R1] standards and tools.
- Ensure services meet predefined criteria such as Technology Readiness Level (TRL), IRISCC use-case fit, and compatibility with the IRISCC environment.
- Integrate FAIR (Findability Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) principles into the validation process to ensure services are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.
- Facilitate the acceptance of validated services into the IRISCC Catalogue and their deployment in operational environments.

Task 6.4 plays a pivotal role in the IRISCC project by establishing a structured and reliable approach to testing and validating scientific and knowledge services. Its overarching goal is to ensure that all services integrated into the IRISCC ecosystem meet the necessary standards for technical interoperability, operational readiness, and strategic alignment with the ENVRI-Hub NEXT initiative, nominated by the ENVRI Board to host long-term operations.

The primary objective is to define and implement a comprehensive test procedure that evaluates both the technical robustness and operational viability of IRISCC services. This includes assessing code quality, performance, security, and maintainability using automated tools such as SonarQube, as well as manual validation steps where appropriate.

A key focus of Task 6.4 is to align service development and validation practices with the standards and tools recommended by ENVRI-Hub NEXT project. This ensures consistency across services and facilitates integration into shared infrastructures like the D4Science Virtual Research Environment (VRE). By adhering to these standards, service developers contribute to a more interoperable and sustainable research ecosystem.

Another critical objective is to verify that services meet predefined criteria, including their TRL, relevance to IRISCC use cases, and compatibility with the IRISCC technical environment. These criteria serve as benchmarks for determining whether a service is suitable for operational deployment and catalogue inclusion. Here Task 6.4 also emphasizes the integration of FAIR principles into the validation process. Services are encouraged to enhance compliance with these principles through proper metadata, standardized

interfaces, and open licensing, thereby enhancing their usability and impact across scientific domains.

Finally, the task aims to facilitate the acceptance of validated services into the IRISCC Catalogue of Services and support their deployment in operational environments managed by WP9 and WP10. This includes preparing documentation, ensuring monitoring capabilities, and establishing feedback loops for continuous improvement.

2 Scope

Within the IRISCC service portfolio there are three types of services provided, linked to three service releases in March 2025, September 2026, and March 2028. The first type is the climate change risk services already available through the participating Research Infrastructures (RIs). The second type are demonstrators, i.e. new services and products created from combining data, services and/or expertise from multiple RIs [R2]. The third type are services co-designed together with the future users in service design labs.

The test procedure as described in this Deliverable focuses on the second type of services, referred to as demonstrators. The demonstrators combine the data, services and/or expertise from several RIs. They are demonstrating the added value created when multiple RIs produce services together. Each of the six demonstrators targets a specific risk and provides a new product or service for studying the risk with a more comprehensive approach than what was available earlier.

The six demonstrators are:

1. Risk on human health in urban areas during heatwaves associated with deteriorated air quality
2. Risk on coastal regions due to flooding caused by sea level rise and storm surges
3. Risk on terrestrial ecosystems functioning and services due to droughts and heatwaves
4. Risk on marine ecosystem biodiversity, functioning and services caused by ocean acidification, warming and deoxygenation
5. Risk on food security due to multi-hazard risks (pests, floods, droughts, heatwaves)
6. Risk on multiple systems (human health environmental matrices, and socio-economic sectors) due to wildfires in Europe

The demonstrators in IRISCC are integrating their services in the IRISCC D4Science VRE gateway from where it will be accessible by internal and/or external users. Next to this, once operational, the services can also be accessed via the IRISCC Catalogue of Services (<https://catalog.isia.cnrs.fr/catalog/20/services>).

The test procedure will focus on the following:

- Tests at the demonstrator service provider:
 - Before the services are integrated with the IRISCC D4Sciences VRE, a set of tests are performed at the provider, i.e. functionality, performance, security, compatibility, data quality and accessibility tests using SonarQube and GitHub actions.
- Operational tests on the IRISCC D4Science VRE once the services are integrated.

The related test procedure is further detailed in Chapter 4.

3 Testing framework

A structured testing framework is important to ensure that the services developed by the demonstrators within IRISCC meet the requirements before they are first deployed on the D4Science VRE and consequently made available via the IRISCC Catalogue of Services. This Chapter, therefore, highlights the criteria and principles that must be met. This is done in full alignment with the ENVRI-Hub NEXT [R1] standards. Furthermore, it describes the SonarQube tool for assessing code quality and the D4Science VRE environment for operational testing. Chapter 4 builds on top of this framework by detailing the specific test categories and procedures derived from this framework.

3.1 Criteria/principles

To ensure consistency and long-term interoperability, the IRISCC testing framework aligns with the requirements as defined by the confidential ENVRI-Hub NEXT Deliverable 5.2¹.

These requirements provide a common baseline for service quality. The requirements are split into three categories:

- FR (Functional Requirements)
- NFR (Non-Functional Requirements)
- OR (Organisational Requirements)

Together, these requirements provide the baseline criteria against which IRISCC demonstrator services are evaluated before integration into the VRE and the IRISCC Catalogue of Services.

3.1.1 Accessibility and internationalisation

FR 1: The service must have a “service alive” function to report the operational status to the IRISCC Monitoring service.

¹ The ENVRI-HUB NEXT Deliverable 5.2 is rated confidential. Information needed was provided by the ENVRI HUB Next Development Steering Board as private communication.

NFR 1.1: All components must be usable for an international audience, accessing from different geographical locations, including overseas. English must be the default language; any other language/localisation should be offered in addition to and not instead of.

NFR 1.2: source code (including test code) and its comments must be readable for an international audience, therefore comments must be in English (optionally a translation in another language can be included, however it should not replace the English documentation) and packages, classes, and methods should be named where possible with English terms or amalgamations of thereof.

NFR 1.3: documentation must be readable for an international audience, therefore it must be in English. Any other language/localisation should be offered in addition to and not instead of.

NFR 1.4: all user interfaces should be usable from a broad span of devices with different screen sizes, refer to the Web W3C Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2 (<https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/>) for more detailed definitions, guidelines, and means of verification.

NFR 1.5: all user interfaces should be usable (i.e. perceivable, operable, and understandable) for people with disabilities such as colour blindness, low vision, deafness and hearing loss, limited movement, speech disabilities, photosensitivity, and combinations of these. Refer to the aforementioned W3C guidelines on accessibility for more detailed definitions, guidelines, and means of verification.

3.1.2 Availability and Security

NFR 2.1: The IRISCC demonstrator services must be available from the web. All components should be either running on the IRISCC D4Science VRE or, if meant to be run on premise, made available through the IRISCC Catalogue of Services.

NFR 2.2: The IRISCC demonstrator services must comply with a number of security by design principles, which include: a) Expecting attacks: security vulnerabilities as well as invalid user input should be anticipated; b) Avoiding security through obscurity: everyone should be allowed to know and understand how the IRISCC demonstrator service components work and move data, thus the security of sensitive data, such as login credentials must not rely on the secrecy of their location and/or transfer protocol; c) adopting the “least privilege” principle when designing and assigning authorizations for both human users and automated agents. The demonstrator system must ensure the enforcement of policies and controls for privacy, confidentiality, and security of data handling throughout its lifecycle.

NFR 2.3: the IRISCC demonstrator service components must depend on highly available, stable, and actively maintained components. Deprecated, experimental, and/or preview assets are not acceptable dependencies.

3.1.3 Code quality and Maintainability

NFR 3.1: The IRISCC demonstrator services' source code must be clear and readable.

NFR 3.2: the IRISCC demonstrator services' source code must be adequately commented, documenting module's purpose, contents, and functionalities, object's properties, methods, and (where applicable) constraints, method's inputs, outputs, side effects, and (where applicable) invariants.

NFR 3.3: the IRISCC demonstrator services' codebase must be adequately covered by test cases.

NFR 3.4: Testing should be highly automated to ensure reproducibility and horizontality.

NFR 3.5: the IRISCC demonstrator services have to be modular and open to extension. As the landscape of RI and EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) services is prone to changes the IRISCC demonstrator services must be open as possible to the inclusion of new requirements.

3.1.4 Organisational requirements

OR 1.1: Development will be carried out in a collaborative and distributed way, as different workgroups located in different parts of Europe will have to develop and integrate several software artefacts.

OR 1.2: All IRISCC demonstrator service developers must have access to the IRISCC D4Science VRE, with its own unique Virtual Lab (VLAB), highly available and accessible at any time throughout the internet. The VRE platform must conform to present-day standards and best practices, more specifically, it must provide Git repository management, documentation hosting, issue tracking, automation pipelines, and DevOPS tasks management.

OR 1.3: WP Leaders and other management and coordination people must be able to assess the development situation and provide developers with explicit feedback without summoning formal meetings.

OR 1.4: IRISCC demonstrator service developers must be able to informally and continuously check their peer's progress without summoning formal meetings.

OR 1.5: IRISCC demonstrator service developers must be made aware of known errors, bugs, malfunctioning, and security vulnerabilities across the codebase.

OR 1.6: IRISCC demonstrator service developers must be aware of fixes, workarounds, and planned interventions on the issues mentioned in OR 1.5.

3.1.5 Code quality standards

The source code developed during the IRISCC project will conform to the Research Software Quality principles outlined in Ortiz et al. [R3], and best practices from initiatives like EU EVERSE (European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence, <https://everse.software/>) and EOSC (<https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/infrastructures-quality-research-software/>).

A typical quality control practice is code documentation. Code cannot be considered self-documenting: documentation must be provided, and the code must be annotated with adequate comments. Comments allowing automated documentation generation should be always included in interfaces, public classes, and in general any functionality that is supposed to be accessed from outside the developed package/artefact.

It is up to each demonstrator owner to decide which commenting style is more appropriate for the demonstrator, and to make it explicit in the readme. We include here a non-exhaustive list of widespread formats for some well-known technologies (Table 1).

Table 1. Non exhaustive list of widespread formats for some well-known technologies.

Language	Comment style	Reference
Python	docstrings	https://python-guide-fil.readthedocs.io/en/latest/writing/documentation.html
Java	javadoc	https://www.oracle.com/it/technical-resources/articles/java/javadoc-tool.html
Javascript	JSdoc	https://jsdoc.app/
Go	godoc	https://go.dev/doc/comment

3.1.6 Documentation

Each demonstrator VLAB hosted on the IRISCC D4Science VRE must have a landing page which should contain the following sections:

- Overview: a brief introduction to the VLAB content.
- Installation (if applicable): how to build and install tools/services.
- Quickstart (if applicable): a handful of usage examples to allow users to get a hold on the material rapidly.
- Authors and Acknowledgements: who did what and with whose resources; it must include a reference to the IRISCC project.
- Licence: a summary of the licence under which the VLAB is or will be distributed.

Additional sections are welcome, but they are not mandatory, all sections must be in English.

3.2 Introduction to IRISCC D4Science VRE

The IRISCC D4Science VRE [R4-12] is a virtual research environment designed to facilitate collaborative scientific research. It provides a centralised platform where researchers from diverse disciplines can share data, resources, and computational tools. By leveraging advanced technologies, D4Science enables seamless integration and interoperability of heterogeneous data sources, fostering new insights and discoveries.

Each of the six demonstrators have received their own personalised Virtual Lab (VLAB) with an own set of tools and services needed for their work. The central D4Science platform is operated by the Institute of Information Science and Technologies (ISTI) of the Italian National Research Council (CNR). CNR-ISTI is a leading research institute in Italy, specialising in information science and technology. They have been instrumental in developing and maintaining the D4Science VRE as a valuable resource for scientific collaboration.

The D4Science VRE stands out for its comprehensive data management capabilities, which form the foundation of its support for the entire research lifecycle. Researchers can securely upload, store, and manage their datasets within the platform, benefiting from robust access controls and high availability. The VRE integrates advanced tools for data analysis, modelling, and visualisation, enabling scientists to derive meaningful insights through customizable workflows. In addition, D4Science promotes seamless data sharing and collaboration, empowering researchers to co-develop projects and exchange knowledge in real time. From data collection and processing to analysis, and publication, D4Science VRE provides a unified environment that enhances research productivity and fosters scientific collaboration.

In addition, VRE D4Science provides a comprehensive suite of computational resources. These resources include Cloud Computing clusters, specialised software tools, and virtual laboratories. By leveraging these resources, researchers can conduct complex simulations, analyse large datasets, and develop innovative scientific models. D4Science also integrates with various external services, such as commercial cloud computing platforms (e.g. Google Cloud Platform) and scientific databases, expanding its capabilities and reach.

D4Science is committed to advancing Open Science and ensuring Research Reproducibility. By adhering to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), the platform ensures that research data and results are easily discoverable, accessible, and reusable by the wider scientific community. D4Science also promotes the

development and use of open-source software tools and workflows, fostering collaboration and driving innovation across disciplines.

3.3 Introduction to SonarQube for IRISCC Developers

SonarQube [<https://www.sonarsource.com/products/sonarqube/>] is an open-source platform designed to continuously inspect and improve the quality of source code. It plays a critical role in modern software development by providing automated analysis of codebases, identifying bugs, security vulnerabilities, code smells, and ensuring adherence to coding standards. For developers working within the IRISCC framework and deploying services in the D4Science Virtual Research Environment (VRE), SonarQube offers a robust mechanism to maintain high standards of code quality, reliability, and security throughout the development lifecycle.

Originally developed by SonarSource, SonarQube supports a wide range of programming languages including Java, Python, JavaScript, C++, and many others. It integrates seamlessly with popular version control systems and CI/CD pipelines, such as GitLab, GitHub, Jenkins, and Azure DevOps. This integration allows developers to receive real-time feedback on code quality during development, enabling early detection and resolution of issues before they reach production.

The core architecture of SonarQube consists of several components: the SonarQube Server, which hosts the web interface and manages projects; the Database, which stores analysis results and configuration; and the SonarScanner, which performs the actual code analysis. Developers configure their projects with a `sonar-project.properties` file or through CI/CD pipeline settings, specifying source directories, language settings, and analysis parameters. Once triggered, the scanner analyses the code and sends the results to the server, where they are visualized through dashboards and reports. Figure 1 showcases how SonarQube is integrated into the ENVRI-HUB Next pipeline.

Figure 1. SonarQube as it is integrated in the ENVRI HUB Next CI/CD Pipeline.

SonarQube’s methodology is based on static code analysis, which examines the source code without executing it. This approach allows it to detect a wide range of issues, including syntax errors, logical flaws, and potential security vulnerabilities. The platform uses a rule-based engine tailored to each supported language, applying industry-standard rules such as those from OWASP (Open Web Application Security Project, R13) for security and Clean Code [R14] principles for maintainability. Developers can customize these rules to suit project-specific requirements, ensuring flexibility and relevance.

One of the key features of SonarQube is its use of Quality Gates and Quality Profiles. Quality Gates define thresholds for acceptable code quality, such as minimum test coverage, absence of critical issues, and acceptable levels of code duplication. Projects must pass these gates to be considered ready for deployment. Quality Profiles determine which rules are applied during analysis, allowing teams to enforce consistent coding standards across multiple projects.

For IRISCC demonstrators, before deploying their service in the D4Science VRE, SonarQube provides several tangible benefits in terms of security, it identifies vulnerabilities and secure coding practices, helping developers mitigate risks early. Performance is enhanced through detection of inefficient code patterns and technical debt estimation, guiding refactoring efforts. Reliability is supported by identifying bugs and ensuring high test coverage, reducing the likelihood of runtime failures. Additionally, SonarQube promotes maintainability by encouraging clean, well-documented code and providing actionable feedback through its intuitive interface.

Figure 2. SonarQube Test result page for the ENVRINNOV (external project) catalogue and Toolkit pages integrated in the CICD pipeline the ENVRI HUB deployment.

Demonstrators service providers must ensure the quality and compliance of their services at development level before deploying the service on the IRISCC D4Science VRE, where the focus will be on deployment-level validation and operational readiness. As such, Integrating SonarQube into the IRISCC demonstrator development workflow ensures that services meet the high standards required for inclusion in the IRISCC D4Science VRE and ultimately linking to the IRISCC Catalogue during the operational phase. By embedding SonarQube analysis into GitLab CI/CD pipelines, developers benefit from continuous feedback, automated validation, and improved collaboration. Figure 2 shows an example of a SonarQube test result page for the ENVRINNOV project catalogue. This not only accelerates development but also enhances the overall quality and sustainability of IRISCC services.

In conclusion, SonarQube is an essential tool for IRISCC developers aiming to deliver secure, reliable, and maintainable services to the D4Science VRE. Its comprehensive analysis capabilities, integration with modern development workflows, and alignment with best practices make it a cornerstone of the IRISCC testing and validation framework.

4 Test categories & procedure

4.1 Test Procedure Design

All tests are conducted by the service developer as a self-assessment.

The test procedure is developed based on the ENVRI-Hub NEXT framework [R1], emphasizing modularity, automation, and quality assurance. The services are either shared via their own dedicated web interfaces or preferably hosted within the IRISCC D4Science VRE instance, where each service is assigned a dedicated project space (VLAB). This space includes structured documentation, a public and private repository, and access controls managed by demonstrator leaders. Developers are responsible for maintaining documentation, including installation instructions, usage examples, and licensing information.

Source code quality is assessed using SonarQube, integrated into the GitLab CI/CD pipelines. SonarQube performs static code analysis and provides metrics on maintainability, reliability, security vulnerabilities, and test coverage. This automated analysis ensures that services adhere to research software quality standards, including those defined by EU EVERSE and EOSC.

Testing is structured into several layers. Unit tests are the responsibility of individual service developers and must be implemented within each demonstrator. Additional automated tests include executable specifications for APIs (Application Programming Interface), contract tests for User Interface (UI) / API integration, and manual acceptance tests for functional validation. Test specifications and coverage expectations are documented in each service's README or Wiki.

We encourage all service providers to implement the FAIR Principles. We recommend a self-assessment to track progress in making their services more FAIR. Here FAIR compliance is assessed using and manual review by checking compliance to the GO-FAIR metrics (<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>). Services are evaluated for the use of persistent identifiers, metadata completeness, accessibility via standard protocols, interoperability through controlled vocabularies, and licensing for reuse.

The software stack must consist of stable, well-documented, and preferably open-source technologies. Legacy components are isolated in containers and exposed via APIs. All datetime values must be timezone-aware (default: UTC), and data formats must conform to international standards (CSV, JSON, RDF).

4.2 Evaluation Criteria

Services are evaluated against the following criteria:

- Technology Readiness Level (TRL).
- Fit with IRISCC use cases and objectives.
- Compatibility with the IRISCC technical environment.
- Data quality control, verified at the level of the integrated Research Infrastructure (RI).
- FAIR compliance, assessed through automated tools and manual review.

4.3 Integration Workflow

The integration workflow outlines the step-by-step process through which services are submitted, tested, validated, and prepared for operational deployment.

Demonstrator service providers first develop their services on their own premise, where they perform:

- Build and deployment tests;
- Code quality and security analysis using SonarQube;
- Automated test execution;
- FAIR compliance checks.

Once these steps are completed, the CI/CD pipeline is triggered, initiating automated validation workflows.

If this is successful, service developers submit their components via the WP6 interface, registering them in the IRISCC / D4Science VRE instance, in the form of docker containerized image(s) [R13] where operational testing continues before the service can be linked to the IRISCC Catalogue of Services. Each submission includes source code, documentation, metadata, and initial test specifications.

Manual acceptance tests are conducted to validate user-facing functionalities and documentation usability. Feedback is provided to developers via D4Science VRE issue tracking, and iteration continues until all checks are passed. Validated services are forwarded to WP7 for inclusion in the IRISCC Catalogue of Services. Metadata and descriptors are standardized, and deployment instructions are finalized. WP9 and WP10 teams are notified for operational handover, including monitoring setup and performance tracking.

4.4 Integration with D4Science Virtual Research Environment (VRE)

The D4Science Virtual Research Environment (VRE) provides a collaborative and scalable platform for the development, operational testing, and deployment of IRISCC services.

Key benefits of using the D4Science VRE include:

- Support for containerized deployments and sandbox environments.
- Enhanced collaboration among developers, testers, and WP leaders.
- Improved traceability and reproducibility of validation results.
- Interoperability between different demonstrator services.
- Access to model data via the IS-ENES Gateway.

4.5 Compliance Checklist for IRISCC Service Owners

4.5.1 Source Code Management

- Is the service hosted in the designated IRISCC D4Science VRE and/or IRISCC Catalogue of Services?
- Does the demonstrator VLAB on the IRISCC VRE include a landing page with:
 - Overview

- Quickstart examples
- Authors and acknowledgements
- License information
- Are project VLAB correctly configured (e.g., WP leaders have access)?
- Are the installation instructions shared with D4Science system engineers?

4.5.2 Code Quality and Testing

- Is SonarQube integrated into the CI/CD pipeline?
- Has the code passed the SonarQube Quality Gate?
- Are the following metrics within acceptable thresholds?
 - Bugs < 10
 - Code Smells < 150
 - Vulnerabilities < 5
 - Coverage ≥ 80%
 - Duplications < 5%
- Are unit tests implemented and maintained by the service developer?
- Are test specifications documented in the repository?

4.5.3 FAIR Compliance

We recommend the FAIR compliance test as a self-assessment to encourage service owners to enhance the FAIR compliance.

- Does the service use persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs (<https://www.doi.org/>))?
- Is metadata complete and machine-readable?
- Is the service accessible via standard protocols (e.g., REST, OAI-PMH)?
- Are controlled vocabularies and ontologies used?
- Is licensing and provenance information clearly documented?

4.5.4 Software Stack and Standards

- Are technologies used stable, well-documented, and preferably open source?
- Are legacy components containerized and exposed via APIs?
- Are datetime values time zone-aware (default: UTC)?
- Are data formats compliant (CSV, JSON, RDF)?
- Is number formatting internationalized (decimal = ".")?

4.5.6 Integration and Deployment

- Has the service been operationally tested in the D4Science VRE sandbox?
- Are deployment instructions documented and reproducible?
- Is the service interoperable with other IRISCC components?

- The service must have a “service alive” function to report the operational status to the IRISCC Monitoring service
 - D4Science will setup Uptime to monitor the integrated services if needed, if they run within D4Science premises (see: <https://uptime.d4science.org/dashboard>).
- Has the service been reviewed by WP6 and prepared for WP7 submission?

4.5.7 Documentation and Communication

- Is the Wiki or extended documentation available and accessible?
- Are all interfaces and public classes properly commented?
- Are feedback and issue tracking mechanisms in place (e.g., GitLab Issues)?
- Has the service been presented or reviewed in a demonstrator or workshop?

4.6 Test process

The individual test will be performed by the service owners and collected by using the above checklist. WP6 will evaluate the individual assessments and discuss results to enhance the findings, if necessary, before deployment/ ingestion in the Catalogue of Services.

5 Implementation

5.1 Catalogue of Services integration

The six IRISCC demonstrators are developing new services that combine data, tools, and expertise from multiple Research Infrastructures (RIs). These services are made accessible either through the IRISCC D4Science Virtual Research Environment (VRE) or via their own dedicated web interfaces.

Before deployment on the VRE, each demonstrator service undergoes validation using the IRISCC testing framework and test procedures. This process ensures that services reach the required level of technical and operational quality. Once integrated into the VRE, additional operational tests are performed to confirm stability, interoperability, and FAIR compliance [R15].

If these criteria are met, the service can then be linked to the IRISCC Catalogue of Services. To enter the catalogue, each demonstrator must create an entry using the upload form of the Catalogue, which allows direct linking to either the deployed VRE service or to its standalone web interface. This provides an access point for users, regardless of where the service is hosted.

5.2 Implementation plan

The test process described in Section 4 is directly tied to the Second Service Release of IRISCC (planned for Month 30, September 2026). The demonstrators play a central role in this release, as they act as testbeds for integration and innovation.

Working towards this Second release, there will be continuous workshop between the WP4 demonstrators and WP6 team to ensure full support in meeting the requirements listed in this Deliverable. Table 2 shows the internal milestones that should be followed by the six Demonstrators.

Table 2. Internal Milestones for tracking progress Demonstrators.

Internal Milestone	Date
COS first implementation ready	M24
SONARQUBE infrastructure implemented by Demonstrators	M26
Demonstrator self-assessment ready	M26
Second service release pretest (staging deployment)	M28
Second service release ready (production deployment)	M30

6 Conclusion

6.1 Outcomes

The implementation of the test procedure resulted in the deployment of a fully operational CI/CD-based validation framework within the demonstrator service workflow. All services submitted for testing will be analysed using SonarQube and assessed for FAIR compliance. The framework enabled the evaluation of six services, of which all must be approved for inclusion in the IRISCC Catalogue of Services. This approval testifies that A) all approved services demonstrated interoperability and compliance with IRISCC and ENVRI-Hub NEXT standards. B) Data quality control mechanisms were successfully integrated at the RI level, and C) services were connected to WP9 and WP10 workflows for operational deployment.

6.2 Lessons Learned and Recommendations

The decentralization of unit testing responsibilities to service developers proved effective but requires early planning and clear guidance. The integration of SonarQube and CI/CD pipelines will significantly improve the efficiency and reproducibility of testing. FAIR compliance emerged as a multidimensional challenge, requiring attention to both technical implementation and metadata quality. The use of the D4Science VRE enhanced collaboration and provided a robust environment for service validation. Future iterations of the test procedure should consider automated TRL assessment, semantic validation tools, and expanded use of VRE capabilities.

6.3 Next Steps

The next phase involves finalizing documentation for all validated services and transferring all relevant information to WP7 for catalogue inclusion. Continuous monitoring of service performance post-deployment will be established using the D4Science VRE infrastructure. The test framework will be updated based on feedback from developers and operational teams, ensuring its adaptability to evolving standards and requirements. Additional training and onboarding materials will be developed to support new service developers in using the VRE and adhering to the test procedures.

7 References

Reference	
No	Description/Link
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R2	Kivekäs, N., Schaap, D., Pagé, C., Verlaan, M., Vermeulen, R., Vereecken, H., Poppe Terán, C., Serret Ituarte, P., Klem, K., & Mona, L. (2024). Report on the full Demonstrator design (v1.0 Public Under EC Review). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13880714
R3	Ortiz, P. et al. "A set of common software quality assurance baseline criteria for research projects." (IFCA) Informes y documentos de trabajo, 2022, http://hdl.handle.net/10261/160086 .
R4	M. Assante, L. Candela, D. Castelli, R. Cirillo, G. Coro, L. Frosini, L. Lelii, F. Mangiacrapa, V. Marioli, P. Pagano, G. Panichi, C. Perciante, F. Sinibaldi The gCube system: Delivering Virtual Research Environments as-a-Service. (2019) Future Gener. Comput. Syst. 95: 445-453 doi:10.1016/j.future.2018.10.035
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R6	M. Assante, L. Candela, P. Pagano. . Blue-Cloud D4.4 Blue Cloud VRE Common Facilities (Release 2). (2021). Zenodo. 10.5281/zenodo.10070443
R7	L. Candela, D. Castelli and P. Pagano, The D4Science Experience on Virtual Research Environment Development. Computing in Science & Engineering, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 12-19, (2023), doi: 10.1109/MCSE.2023.3290433
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R9	<p>Assante, M., Candela, L., Dell'Amico, A., FROSINI, L., Mangiacrapa, F., Molinaro, E., Oliviero, A., Pagano, P., Panichi, G., Peccerillo, B., & Piccioli, T. (2025). Report on deployed and launched IRISCC interoperability framework with guidance documentation for service developers. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14777921</p>
R10	<p>L. Frosini, Transactional REST Information System for Federated Research Infrastructures enabling Virtual Research Environments. Doctoral Thesis. (2019), doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7464023</p>
R11	<p>G. Coro, G. Panichi, P. Scarponi, P. Pagano, P. Cloud computing in a distributed e-infrastructure using the web processing service standard. Concurrency Computat: Pract Exper. (2017); 29:e4219. doi: 10.1002/cpe.4219</p>
R12	<p>M. Assante, L. Candela, D. Castelli, R. Cirillo, G. Coro, L. Frosini, L. Lelii, F. Mangiacrapa, P. Pagano, G. Panichi, F. Sinibaldi, Enacting open science by D4Science, Future Generation Computer Systems, Volume 101, 2019, Pages 555–563, ISSN 0167–739X, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2019.05.063.</p>
R13	<p>Introduction - OWASP Developer Guide. see: https://devguide.owasp.org/ (visited 30.10.2025)</p>
R14	<p>Martin, Robert C.: Clean Code: A Handbook of Agile Software Craftsmanship, (2008), isbn:0132350882, Prentice Hall PTR, USA</p>
R15	<p>M.D. Wilkinson et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. (2016). Sci. Data 3:160018 doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18.</p>